

Energy-Classical Frequency in Quantum Oscillator Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 20, 2022

In Part I we noted that the quantum oscillator result $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ implies that for $\exp(-iEt)$ there are special times proportional to $1/E$ which in turn are proportional to $1/\omega$ which is proportional to the classical cycling time of the oscillator. In other words for oscillators with different ω there are different $1/\omega$ times such that $-Et$ (which is part of a free particle action $A = -Et + px$) is constant i.e. one cannot distinguish as in statistical mechanical equilibrium.

In this note, we consider the free particle action in more detail. From $A = -Et + px$ there are special times ($1/E$) and lengths $1/p$ proportional to wavelength such that different E and p values when multiplied by these times and length have the same value. Furthermore $A = 0$ for this values. We argue that it is this feature of px in $\exp(ipx)$ which is responsible for the energy of an oscillator being proportional to ω , the classical angular frequency. Thus the idea of a special length (wavelength) such that different p 's when multiplied by $1/p$ produce the same value leads to a quantum energy such that $1/E$ is proportional to a physical cycling time in the classical problem. Thus different ω 's lead to $E/\hbar\omega$ being constant just as p/p is constant.

Classical Oscillator

The classical oscillator's energy conservation equation as noted in Part I is of the form of a dot product:

$$m/2 \dot{v}v + k/2 xx = \frac{1}{2} kAA \quad \text{where } A \text{ is amplitude} \quad ((1))$$

This is also of the form of a right angle triangle equation so one may postulate $x = A \cos(\omega t)$ which leads to:

$$m/k \omega\omega = 1 \quad \text{where } v = d/dt A \cos(\omega t) \quad \text{or } \omega = \sqrt{k/m} \quad ((2))$$

Thus the parameters in the system m, k constitute the physical frequency which is linked to the cycling time.

At first glance one might expect that quantum mechanics has nothing to do with this classical frequency even though m and k are part of the Schrodinger equation. The quantum energy $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$, however, is directly proportional to the classical frequency. We try to investigate why.

Quantum Oscillator

The time-independent Schrodinger equation is of the form:

$$KE_{\text{average}}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

, so there is a $v_{rms}(x)$ which is classical, but it is not of interest usually. Furthermore the classical form ((3)) does not indicate which discrete E values arise. It is the special form of $KE_{average}(x)$ in quantum mechanics which yields quantum results. In particular:

$$KE_{average}(x) = \text{classical } KE(x) \text{ value} = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W \quad ((4))$$

Where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. This form, however, ultimately follows from $\exp(ipx)$ which is the free particle wavefunction i.e.:

$$KE_{average} = \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{From this: } -i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

The important feature is that p scales x in the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which also happens to be both the relativistic and nonrelativistic free particle classical action if one writes $v = x/t$. In previous notes we argued that x and t should be considered as independent and that there is a special time proportional to $1/E$ and a special length proportional to $1/p$ such that A at these values is 0. In other words one may have uncertainty in t and x (cycles) which do not change A . Expressed differently, different p (momenta) have different wavelengths such that px is a constant i.e. one cannot distinguish p from p/p . This is reminiscent of statistical equilibrium scenarios where there is a loss of information e.g. $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ used to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

We argue that it is this feature of a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to the classical oscillator angular frequency being proportional to the discrete quantum energy. In other words, only quantum energies such that $Et = E/w =$ independent of k, m result.

In particular, $\frac{p^2}{2m} W = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W$ so average kinetic energy scales as $1/(xx)$ while potential energy of an oscillator scales as xx . This suggests the possibility of combining parameters to define a new x such that no parameters appear on the LHS of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. As shown in Part I, y such that $yy = \sqrt{km} \ xx$ satisfies this condition with $E \rightarrow E \sqrt{m/k}$. The LHS of the Schrodinger equation depends only on y which ranges from $-\infty$ to ∞ so the RHS cannot contain m or k . Thus:

$$E \text{ is proportional to } w \quad ((7))$$

In other words for $\exp(-iEt)$, t proportional to $1/E$ is also proportional to $1/w$ which is proportional to the classical cycling time of an oscillator. This is a direct result of the form $\exp(ipx)$ with p scaling x and this form for a free particle follows from special relativity i.e. from the Action = $-Et + px$ and the idea that $t = 1/E$ and $x = 1/p$ leaves A unchanged so that there is an uncertainty cycle within these time and x ranges. This is why t and x are independent within this range even though there is a velocity as the overall free particle moves along.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum oscillator result $E = \hbar \omega (n + 0.5)$ such that energy is proportional to $1/\omega$ which in turn is proportional to the classical cycling time follows from the quantum free particle form $\exp(ipx)$. In other words p scales x so if $x \rightarrow ax$ then $p \rightarrow p/a$. More explicitly $-i\hbar d/dx$ is the momentum operator and so one may see the scaling explicitly. The form px follows from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which also happens to be both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical free particle action. For $t = 1/E$ and $x = 1/p$, $A = 0$ so there is a special cycling range with t and x independent such that there is uncertainty in x and t even though there is a constant velocity x/t . This leads to the quantum idea of frequency and wavelength which accompanies free particle motion. It is this feature of $\exp(ipx)$ which carries over into the quantum oscillator problem. The classical problem yields angular frequency $\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$, but scaling in the quantum case allows one to introduce y such that $yy = xx \sqrt{km}$. This scaling follows directly from the form $\exp(ipx)$. This form ensures that given any p there is a length proportional to $1/p$ such that the product is a constant. In the oscillator case i.e. the time independent Schrodinger case, this scaling ensures there is a t proportional to $1/E$ which does not allow one to distinguish between different oscillators i.e. different ω 's. This means E must be proportional to ω which it is due to the scaling feature. In other words the LHS of the Schrodinger equation may be written solely in terms of y with no m, k parameters. Thus $E \sqrt{m/k}$ on the RHS must be independent of these parameters meaning E is proportional to $\sqrt{k/m}$.